

TRANSFORMING JOURNALISM AND COMMUNICATION EDUCATION: A FOCUS ON BANGLADESH AND PAPUA NEW GUINEA

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***Abstract:** The study focuses on Journalism and Communication education in developing countries that indicates a compromise and balance of traditional outlay and modern technology but resulted to a mismatch of 'slow march to fast music'. Expansion of media is not commensurate with the population in both the countries studied. It has been observed that with thriving democracy, the growth of mass media is reflective with the growth of media education in Bangladesh, whereas the growth of media and the state of democracy both are in formative stage in Papua New Guinea (PNG). It was examined that media in Bangladesh have been contributing potentially to create pluralistic democratic values to a densely populated country. Newspapers and TV channels draw communication graduates from public and private universities. The study envisaged that Papua New Guinea, an independent country in 1975, and world's most diversified nation with highest number of languages, 823 languages among 6.5 million people, craving for a working democracy with meager state of media in the country. On the other hand, alternative media education as conceptualized as 'Civic Journalism' got a trial in one of the public universities. It has been focused to rural areas and on the issues like human rights, good governance, gender, democracy, rule of law and justice, and environment.*

***Keywords:** Communication, journalism education, alternative media, media, exposure, community radio.*

Introduction

Media education has expanded with the development of mass media and their expansion of exposure in most of the developing countries. The situation of media education comprising education on journalism, communication, and mass media show that there is a relation of development of democracy and growth of media education. This perception is echoed by Assistant Director-General for Communication and Information of UNESCO, in the forwarding of the publication on UNESCO Series on Journalism Education. It has been

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stated that over the last few years, the number of news media outlets in developing countries and emerging democracies has grown rapidly. “There has been an increased recognition of the crucial role of journalism in promoting democracy, and this has created an urgent demand for well-trained journalists.” (UNESCO, 2007:4). UNESCO intended to organize regional meetings to develop national bibliographies and discuss how the curricula can be adapted according to the needs and resources of different countries. The document underscored that to practice and upgrade their journalistic skills are essential tools for the underpinning of key democratic principles that are fundamental to the development of every country. (UNESCO, 2007). Although it has been recognized to upgrade the journalistic training and education but the development of media education did not take place so far in a homogenous way in all the developing countries.

Education in Journalism in Bangladesh and in Papua New Guinea: Prevailing situation and scope of new approach

Journalism and Mass Communication Education in Bangladesh

The Department of Mass Communication and Journalism in the University of Dhaka has been playing pioneer role in promoting media education in Bangladesh since its inception in 1962. On October 24, 1962 the classes of the first Diploma course began with an enrolment of 16 students selected on the basis of written aptitude test and viva-voce examination. In 1968-69 academic session a two-year Master’s degree (MA) programme was introduced. The birth of a new country in 1971 led journalism educators to acknowledge the growing need for communication in the modern world. Consequently, an undergraduate programme – a three-year Honours course – was introduced, the diploma course was discarded. (Rahman, 1999: 141-2) The department was renamed as the Department of Mass Communication and Journalism in place of Journalism Department at the University of Dhaka (DU). The Department has been offering four-year Bachelor course (BSS) and one year Master course (MSS) for them who have completed BSS. There are Ph.D. research facilities in the Department and a few students are carrying out their research programs under the supervision of department faculties. Every year around 75 students take admission in the first year with a total of 350 students in different programmes pursue studies in undergraduate and post-graduate levels at DU where 18 full time faculties along with a dozen of part-time lecturers provide teaching services.

A variety of courses focusing both print and electronic media are being offered in undergraduate (BSS) and postgraduate levels. They are: Concepts

of Journalism, Concepts of Communication, Reporting, Editing, Feature writing, Mass Communication theories, Communication and society, Development communication, Media management, Health and population communication, Electronic journalism, Video communication, Advertising and copy writing, Public Relations, Communication policy and planning, Television theories and contents, Film studies, Economic reporting, Communication research methodology, Photojournalism, Contemporary affairs, Gender communication, Advanced reporting, Advanced editing and page make-up, etc. With little variation of some subjects most of the public as well as private universities are offering the above mentioned subjects in the country.

Following the trend of Dhaka University and with the demand among students as well as measuring the expansion of media establishments in the country, similar courses have been introduced in Rajshahi University and Chittagong University. Rajshahi University introduced a Bachelor in Social Science (BSS) Honours in Mass Communication in 1992 and followed by a master programme after three years. Chittagong University started degree Honours course in Journalism in 1994 and later master course was also introduced.

Some of the private universities in Bangladesh have ambitious programme of introducing new departments of communication and media education. They are Independent University of Bangladesh (IUB), University of Liberal Arts (ULAB), Daffodil International University (DIU), Stamford University (SU), American International University (AIU) and University of Alternative Development (UODA). Many of them are struggling with Bachelor courses and some of them introduced postgraduate course attracting handful of students.

To showcase media education in Bangladesh one will find that the DU has a media centre equipped with video cameras, editing panels, computers and a photo lab with camera and other equipment to facilitate the students to have practical know-how on different courses. Other public universities in the country have little equipment to support their programme but they lack either proper and well-maintained gadgets or proper persons to handle those gadgets. There is a trend among the academic staff that most of them opt for teaching communication subjects instead of Journalism subjects. Subjects like Media Reporting, Media Editing, and Media Writing are often taken care of by academic faculties with little or no background of professional experience. Other than DU there is a lack of getting proper human resources on the subjects who have professional experience.

One aspect needs attention that many senior academics involved in media teaching feel problems of refreshing themselves with the trend of the modern media technology. Because of their traditional mindset and psychological barrier they are not ready to accept the modern technology and change. Consequently they cannot take part providing media education with the help of new technology. It seems that the gap persists between the senior academics and young student generation. To fill-up this gap there is a need to address fast to keep those matured academics in a proper path of technology-literate with little attention of using modern media equipment. They may be provided with training on modern technology abroad to feel themselves compatible and less shy.

Traditionally, public universities in Bangladesh bear most of the costs of education from the exchequer and the students bear a nominal tuition fees and charges. The public universities cannot supply adequate facilities to the students because of fund constraints. This state of affair has an effect on the maintenance of standard of education. On the contrary, some of the private universities started providing lessons with technological support for some of the media courses, because they get handsome amount of money from students as tuition fees. Recurring costs to carry out courses in the university on media related subjects need plan to develop how they could be made self-sustaining.

Most of the programs were planned to meet the traditional practices in the main stream journalism and heavily concentrated on communication courses. The courses offered on journalism especially, reporting, editing, and feature writing lack real life practices because, traditionally those subjects are taught in a theoretical manner with old materials imagining current situations. The students practice reporting and editing with old materials imagining current news and contemporary news-value. Rarely are they sent to cover the real life situations. Often they are asked to write features covering field studies. Most class rooms for reporting and editing are equipped with several computers and often with Internet. But the class room lacks the newsroom environment and suffers without information updates that to be considered as news to be written by the students. The prevailing academic facilities in the universities, both public and private, although organized mostly with modern electronic gadgets, rarely provide support to the students for their full-length use. Often the set of equipment is not operative and whatever available cannot work because of lack of consumables. The maintenance of media lab is often a mismatch with the modern electronic gadgets in media education. The students at

present are aware of information system through Internet, mobile phone and satellite TV channels at their personal level and many of them show their interests, aptitudes and capabilities to uphold them in their behavior. That is why it is found that many students of Journalism and Communication at DU get attached, of their personal capacities, with media houses beginning from their second year of study.

Communication and Media Education in Papua New Guinea

There are three institutions that provide education in journalism, communication and media. They are the University of Papua New Guinea (UPNG) in Port Moresby, Papua New Guinea University of Technology (PNG Unitech) in Lae, and Divine Word University (DWU) in Madang. UPNG offer Diploma and Bachelor programme in Journalism and Public Relations; DWU offers a two-year Diploma in Communication Arts (Journalism) and B.A in Communication Arts (Journalism); and PNG Unitech offers Diploma and Bachelor in Communication for Development; and also Master of Communication Studies (MCS) course at postgraduate level. In the DWU and Unitech it is found that the number of female students is more than that of male students from very inception of the course (Table-1). At PNG Unitech every year about 25 to 30 students get admission in first year of the two-year Diploma programme and majority of them continue to the third year of the four-year Bachelor Degree programme (B.Tech) in Communication for Development. A masters course, Master of Communication Studies (MCS), was introduced in 2009 for the first time in the Pacific region at PNG Unitech and its second and third batches of students are continuing their education in 2011.

Subjects offered under Diploma in UPNG are: Mass Communication; Print Media Production; News Practice; News Techniques; Practical Report; Community Publishing; and at Bachelor level Mass Media Theory; Information and Communication Technology; Information and Communication Trends and Development; and Research Report Writing.(UPNG, 2010). In DWU under the Department of Communication Arts subjects like Development Communication; Reporting; Editing; Broadcasting are being offered in Diploma and Bachelor courses.

Amanda Watson (2006) mentioned citing David Robie that in the South Pacific region there is a lack of professional training of journalists, poor standards of education and media professionals lack knowledge in political and social institutions. (Robie, 2004a). Nonetheless, journalists are aware of

their collective role as a “watchdog of democracy” (Robie, 2005:30). Watson explained quoting Moore (1995) that training institutions include the University of the South Pacific, which commenced its journalism programme in 1994, and the Pacific Islands News Association coordinates some short courses. Samoa Polytechnic has a one-year course, “Certificate of Achievement in Journalism”. (Watson, 2006:32). Papua New Guinea Media Council also arranges short courses and workshops for journalists. As per Robie’s study Watson (2006) stated “only 5% of the respondents had participated in a short course (Robie, 2005:28). However, 81% of the respondents possessed either a degree or a diploma, and 70% had majored in journalism (ibid: 28-29).”

Divine Word University Department of Communication Arts (Journalism) has affiliation with daily newspapers through which the students can contribute to those papers. The students of DWU have facilities to practice campus radio broadcast and UPNG students participate in producing news and programme for UPNG Campus radio as well. The practice of the professionals mainly in two tabloid daily newspapers is the example of the ‘would be journalists’ which are genuinely confronted as criticisms. Rooney and Papoutsaki (2006:9) have explained that they lack critical and analytical skills and in-depth knowledge of crucial issues that dominate country’s development. They also argued that reporting was often superficial, based on one source, and not properly researched.

Journalism of negative image and Western values in PNG

The portrayal of negative image of the country as well as blaming the Western values of news in the PNG media by the local professionals are observed by several researchers in the country. An argument was forwarded in a research study done in 2004 on ‘The Role of Journalists in PNG’ done by Lawrencia Pirpir (2004) that the journalists are not performing to the best of their professional standards; they are trained using Western concepts that do not relate to the Papua New Guinean way of communication. It has also been argued that “Messages were mostly passed orally, a trend that exists to this day. The PNG media concentrates on the elite over ordinary citizens. ... journalists in this country do not inform the masses....the media concentrates on those that can afford to be informed...” (Pirpir). Rooney *et al* (2004) stated that external and Western influences could be seen in the newspapers that reflect the mindset of the journalists, because the professionals received Western-influenced journalism training. Similarly Wickham said earlier, “... the media is too Western and not attuned to the values and cultures of the

region.” (Wickham, 1996 in Rooney & Papoutsaki, 2006). Broadcast media are dominantly reflecting Western cultural values through EMTV that was evident from the study of Jashua L Kais (2006:189). The study revealed that 45 per cent of respondents opined EMTV reflected Australian values. The respondents stated that Australian and other Western values dominate the broadcasts. It is argued that any effort to imitate the ‘foreign programs end up revealing nothing about PNG cultures’ by the opinion of a female viewer mentioning the name of programme “House and Home and Insait PNG”.

Another study done by Celestine Ove (2008) based on a content analysis of PNG’s two dailies and one weekly newspaper, the *Post-Courier*, *The National* and the *Wantok*, over a five-month period that investigated whether more prominence was given to ‘negative’ stories in the PNG press; and whether the reporters and the editors were influenced by Western news values, which value more “bad news as good news” and pursued the way they did construct and present a ‘negative’ story. Media in PNG, especially the print media became point of criticism by leaders and public as well for the portrayal of negative image of the country. “This negative image stems from the number of reports of corruption, crime, physical and sexual violence, political and economic instability that seem to be predominant in the PNG press.” (Ove, 2008). The same study from a survey among four regions of the country found that there is a general negative perception of the country from what is presented by the print media and 80 per cent of the respondents call for more positive stories for the sake of empowerment.

Mass media in the world’s most diverse society of PNG

Rahman and Islam (2009) showed that according to Audit Bureau of Circulation (ABC), the circulation of *The National* during the January-March period of 2009 averaged 30,439 copies, while the *Post-Courier* was at 21,352 mentioned in the web edition of the *National* (2009). One of the major dailies in the South Pacific, Australian-owned *Post-Courier*, lists Rupert Murdoch's News Ltd. as its majority share with one-third of private investors of Papua New Guinea. The paper covers national and international news, sports, and business and brings out from Monday to Friday and uses Australian Associated Press (AAP) news feed. *The Post-Courier's* circulation dropped after a rival daily newspaper, the Malaysian-owned *The National*, launched in 1994. It gets wire service from Agence France Presse (AFP). Both the newspapers publish daily except weekend apprehending sufficient market.

In case of radio as well as other mass media of PNG it is to be understood along with the fabric of languages and cultures of vastness. Among 823

identified languages, yet only 200 are related, and all are said to be 'grammatically complex'. A few hundred to a few thousand people speak each language. Enga, one native language, is spoken by some 130,000 people, and Melanesian Pidgin serves as the lingua franca. No single medium of communication can address the entire population nor can anyone language get access to the whole nation. The potentials of radio to push any public service message in a developing country have great scope and utility.

The exposure to mass media in PNG is limited with potential coverage and of state-run National Broadcasting Corporation (NBC), and NAU FM commercial broadcast. Rooney Papoutsaki (2006: 1-18) on the media and communication landscape in Papua New Guinea analysed that publicly funded radio in the country is in the hands of bureaucracy which was initially designed to serve a national audience, especially the rural people through Karai national service by 19 Kundu provincial stations in local languages. It has been observed that NBC talk about a bureaucratic, process-oriented culture and takes time to deliver decisions. It is slow to introduce new managerial practices and being contested by public whether NBC is really free.

The Government operates a national radio station and a handful of provincial stations and their news coverage are claimed to be balanced. While BBC (2009) stated in its country profile as, "But funding problems, and the non-payment of power bills, have taken some of the regional radios off the air." The number of radio receiving sets available to people is 410,000 and the total number of TV sets available is 42,000 mentioned in the Press Reference (2009). In 1987, the first TV of PNG, EMTV came into existence and it telecasts national news at 6 pm with repeated transmission at night but major chunk of telecast time is occupied by foreign English serials. National television of PNG has been established on its 34th Independence Day.

It could be argued that as the media in PNG has been portraying the life, society, culture and other socio-economic parameters that have a few implications in the education field. Mass media have not yet got the access to the majority people in the country. Since social indicators as per human development index are not commensurate with the high per capita income level and the people are placed in remote rural areas with diverse linguistic-cultural social setups, it is a real challenge to address any national or regional public service message.

Communication education whatever available in three universities in PNG is limited with traditional focus and media production. Most of the media,

newspapers and TV stations, are owned by foreign companies, neither have diverse population in their minds as social obligation as a developing country, nor do they have capacity to produce local contents for them. Mass media, in general, are urban phenomenon which expose urban and event oriented contents. Understanding local situation, local needs, and local culture and values the academia in the universities has limited contribution serving the students. It has been observed that the teaching of communication and media are not supplemented by depth of education and skill and adequate technological support as well. Availability of experts and specialized education is not easy and sustainable and most of them suffer from local knowledge, local culture and local values.

Traditional coverage by mainstream media in Bangladesh

Coverage of news in most newspapers is traditional with the exotic concept of news. Local cultural context is missing ignoring the involvement of public and societal values. Reporting in general is dominantly urbanised and event oriented. Grass-roots people are mostly ignored in the media due to the traditional practice. Decision-makers and development planners have a little connection with the grass-roots people. Therefore, they get a little information about the needs and reality of the marginalised people which, in a way, leads to the failure of any development initiative. To narrow down the lacuna between the planners and the people, urban and rural, the exposure of mass media with the community people is a must. Journalism and media practice are to be integrated with the majority people's life, aspirations, and their needs. Alternative media such as rural information through Internet, rural theatre, community radio and civic journalism emerged on the prevailing situation.

There is a lack of newer approach in journalistic training and education with the expanding need of civic/development journalism and communication involving development of grass-roots people, human rights issues, good governance, production of TV and broadcast journalism and communication and communication technology. The techniques of reporting, writing, editing and covering these issues need a special approach where the conventional and main stream journalism could not realize fully well. As well, there is no initiative from the media organizations or industry to develop the skill of human resources for practicing civic/development journalism.

Besides, colleges in Bangladesh offer many other subjects that have no relation with life skill development or any other practical utilities or as driven by the market. Subjects like History, Islamic History, Political Science,

Philosophy, Physics, Chemistry, and so on are traditionally being offered in undergraduate and Bachelor levels in many colleges in Bangladesh. Most of the students, after completion of their courses on those subjects, cannot contribute to their respective fields, because there is not much scope available to offer services on those fields. Whereas, Journalism / Communication / Media studies could be offered as very useful subjects at undergraduate and postgraduate levels in the colleges understanding the expansion and utilities of communication and media. Introduction of new subjects in a college at undergraduate and Bachelor levels are not encouraged by the National University due to its traditional outlook. A breakthrough in this line may shower blessings to the society to have a practical and realistic education for the sustenance of development and information. Specialized area of education like civic/development journalism / communication can be arranged in some of the institutions regionally to facilitate the learners who may provide their skills in a pragmatic way because Bangladesh has got a democratic culture and large population to receive those services.

Media exposure in national level

Media habit of the people is abominably low with low literacy and lack of access to mass media. If we look into the country situation in the National Media Survey (2003) available, we find that exposure to print media such as newspaper and magazine is very low and only 25.7 percent read newspapers (9.3% read everyday, 15% read occasionally, and 1.4% read 1 – 6 days in a week) and 7.9 percent read magazines. Exposure to radio was found as 30.4 percent (11.1% listened everyday, 4.4% listened 1-6 days in a week, and 14.9% listened one or more times in a month). There has been a persistent increase in the viewership of television. TV viewership increased from 31 percent in 1995 to about 61 percent in 2002. The study also showed that TV ownership increased from 8 percent in 1995 to 14 percent in 1998 and then to 25 percent in 2002. News broadcast by BTV is government monitored and the TV authority overlooks the news value of the transmitted news bulletin. Because of government control on BTV, the ruling party gets undue coverage of their events at the cost of the opposition parties. (Rahman, 2007).

Urban-rural Gap

The gap of media exposure is significant and very high between rural and urban population. Newspaper readership including occasional readers was found in 2002 in urban area as 40% and in rural area 19%. Radio listening was found as 24% in urban area and 34% in rural area including listeners who

listen once in a month. Viewers of television were found as 83% urban and 50% rural including people who watched once or more in a month, as per National Media Survey 2003.

Growth of media and professional capacity building

Development of Journalism in the country shows the growth of publications of newspapers and other periodicals along with electronic communication media. Some 375 daily newspapers, a few hundred weeklies and fortnightlies are being published in the country. Beside the government controlled two television channels, Bangladesh Television (BTV), there are 11 private TV channels broadcasting programmes and five new private channels got license for operation. Radio Bangladesh broadcasts with its 11 stations serving the nation as the government mouthpiece and six private radio stations transmit news and entertainment programmes. The Government of Bangladesh issued 14 licenses to Community Radio Stations in the country, which was the result of struggle lead mainly by non-government organizations.

The situation of labour market in Bangladesh is expanding on the field of communication and development and at the same time there is lack of opportunities to upgrade professional capacity in this area. Private media houses always expect that skilled and quality graduates from the universities would join them. Often, the best quality students, after their degree, show interest to provide service to the media houses but most of them are not attracted with standard remuneration. Although media houses developed as industries but they do not contribute to the development of media education in the country in general. They look for public university to supply them with high quality graduates. They sometimes accept students for internship. Private universities are yet to develop strong professional relationship with the media houses. Only when a media professional participates in teaching at an institute ,would maintain mutual relations with that institute.

Bangladesh Radio and Community Radio

The government-owned Bangladesh Betar (radio) is a sleeping giant. It had and still has great potential if it could be used in the right manner. Community radio may somewhat fill that gap. Because, in a democratic country, what we claim for, people cast their vote to elect their leaders, but they are nowhere when it comes to decision making. Community radio could have played an effective platform for these unheard voices and if that happened democracy would have strengthened. Instead of becoming voice of the people, radio in Bangladesh has been represented as voice of the government. Radio is not treated by policymakers as a participatory medium which can be used for community development.

Community radio may cater to the interests of a certain area and broadcast material which is overlooked by more powerful broadcast groups. In that sense emergence of community radio is an alternative way of expression of grassroots or marginalized people who are deprived of participating in expressing their views in the mainstream radio. In a country with mostly rural population, about 70 per cent, and in which only about 20 per cent people are connected to the electricity grid, radio is without a doubt the only mass medium capable of reaching the majority of the population. It reaches people who can't read or write.

The potential for Community Radio and need of media education

In Bangladesh, community radio has a tremendous potential as an educative medium and as a support for technology transfer in the areas like health, natural disaster, education and agriculture. Community radio stations can play a significant role in increasing participation and opinion sharing, improving and diversifying knowledge and skills and in catering to health and cultural needs.

Bangladesh is a country where hundreds of NGOs have been working across the country and their achievements have been acknowledged worldwide. Community radio is such a medium which should be run, managed and owned by the community. Mostly it has been said that the community radio should not be run by NGO or an organisation. The NGOs can at best organise, train and provide technical support. In reality, most of the licenses are awarded to the NGOs. The rural people not only get access to information that has direct impact on their lives, but they will be able to take part in development activities and democratic processes. The community radio programming would likely be a mix of educational, cultural and entertainment programmes where the media graduates of the locality may provide potential service to that cause.

Therefore, there is a strong circumstantial demand that people who aim to be professional in this field, should feel demand to participate in the program to equip themselves in specialized professional career. Local journalists of different newspapers having no professional training urged to participate in such program for a wider professional efficiency as well as to be involved in allied career after having a course in journalism and communication. In a densely populated country like Bangladesh, the utilization of community radio would be highly complemented by the media professionals who have equipped with media education. To fit-in the newly introduced community

radio the media professionals need to be prepared to cater the community people with a newer approach of media production that poses real challenge of development communication or as such. The courses in media schools to be redesigned to match the proper perspective of changing needs of the community. There is an option to understand the mainstream journalism/communication studies and new approach communication/journalism education as mentioned as civic journalism/communication.

Alternative Media Model in Bangladesh

Communication being a potential power and to exercise this means of power into the life of the grass-roots people for their welfare and development, there is a need to reframe the process of communication and dissemination of information in a new approach. Reflections of life and reality of the grass-roots people in mass media towards a change are to be addressed in the perspective of a newer approach. Apart from the main stream journalism and communication a new approach of dissemination of information and motivation emerged with the help of alternative media focusing them in human rights issues, good governance, development agenda, practice of democracy and social behaviour change.

In search of Alternative Model

The scenario of media exposure and pattern of coverage of mainstream journalism lead to search for an alternative model of communication media. The concept of civic journalism is to mean the state of journalism, which involves majority's participation in development process springing them into a change for a better life. To ensure the public domain into the empowerment and good governance with the practice of rights and justice for all and these need to be reflected in mass media. A large number of working journalists and 'would be journalists' in this line were enrolled under a programme of diploma course in Rajshashi University to enhance professional aptitude and skills. Therefore, the need for introducing an alternative approach to the education of journalism as well as media could be claimant.

A rural based country like Bangladesh needs social development by establishing people's rights and promoting good governance and democratic practice at the grass-roots level. It has been evident that the national newspapers cannot reflect fully the reality of the rural life and local activities of the country and more over the capacity of the local newspapers are not satisfactory due to the conceptual shortcomings of reporting, editing and over

all coverage. Practice of civic journalism as well as participatory radio broadcast, as community radio will be right-based, democratic and will contain value of good governance. The government-owned Bangladesh Betar (radio) is a sleeping giant. It had and still has great potential if it could be used in right manner towards development goal. The image of radio as a government mouth-piece has lost the credibility as an effective medium. Taking the present situation of communication and media in Bangladesh, the new approach to civic journalism/ communication will be a natural process to avail the transforming media education besides the mainstream journalism.

Reviewing communication and media situation in Papua New Guinea the perception of accepting their own culture and values instead of Western and negative portrayal of images in the media is not new but to maintain that there is a need of new strategic plan to set the tone for new role of communication to the diverse nation. The national goals and directive principles of the Constitution of Papua New Guinea are set as: Integral human development; Equality and participation; National sovereignty and self-reliance; Natural resources and environment; and Papua New Guinean way of development. These goals may be attained with new communication strategy of innate and integrated use of interpersonal channel and mass media. PNG should have own national media run by them that reflect nation's democratic culture and values of diversity and harmony which may transform the media education from its usual and Western influence.

Table-1: Number of enrolment of male and female students at different courses							
PNG Unitech: 2010				DWU: 2003, 2004, 2005 and 2006			
B. Tech	Male	Female	Total	Diploma	Male	Female	Total
Year 1/ Diploma	12	20	32	2003	14	20	24
Diploma	13	13	26	2004	14	28	42
Year 3	12	14	26	2005	10	25	35
Year 4	5	12	17	2006	7	26	33
MCS				B.A			
Year 1	0	4	4	2005	5	6	11
Year 2	1	3	4	2006	2	10	12

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